

PHYSIOLOGY OF ANIMALS

MORPHOLOGY OF LAYING HEN AND QUAIL EGGS

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Abstract

The effect of the combined use of two forms of benzoic acid and mannanoligosaccharides on the weight and morphology of chicken eggs was studied. The impact of varying doses of the Sal-Zap organic acid complex on quail egg weight and morphology was examined in the study. The results helped identify optimal application rates. A combination of 750 g of concentrated benzoic acid, 200 g/t of coated benzoic acid, and 400 g of Actigen per 1 ton of laying hens' feed demonstrated the most significant results. The use of Sal-Zap at a dosage of 750 g/t in quail feed yielded the highest results. These levels can be recommended for nutritionists specializing in laying hens and quails.

Keywords: benzoic acid, coated benzoic acid, mannanoligosaccharides, Actigen, Sal-Zap, laying hens, quails, eggshell, yolk, albumen.

Eggshells are approximately 95% calcium carbonate, 3.5% organic compounds, and the remaining 1.5% other minerals and non-mineral elements [1]. The eggshell is the first line of defense against external influences and microbial invasion. In addition to the membrane beneath the eggshell, the shell contains internal components such as the albumen and yolk [2]. Shell strength is critical for both table and hatching eggs. The quality and integrity of commercial eggs depend largely on the strength of their shells during collection, storage, and transportation.

The yolk stores energy and other nutrients. The yolk's natural function is to provide complete nutrition to the embryo during embryogenesis. The yolk serves as the body's immune defense and serves as an antioxidant. It contains proteins - building material for the cells and tissues of the future chick, fats - a source of energy for growth and development, carbohydrates - providing energy for the first days of life, vitamins - regulating metabolic processes and ensuring the normal functioning of the body, minerals - the formation of bones, blood and other tissues [3].

Egg albumen is a complex mixture of water (over 85%) and a variety of high-quality proteins (ovoalbumin, ovotransferrin, lysozyme, and others) with minimal fat and carbohydrates. The protein is the basis for embryonic nutrition, provides physical and chemical protection for the yolk, and has bactericidal properties. The protein also contains B vitamins [4].

Benzoic acid belongs to the group of simple aromatic carboxylic acids. Benzoic acid has been shown to increase live weight gain and improve feed conversion in broiler chickens; however, high doses of benzoic acid have been reported to negatively impact productivity. Benzoic acid, protected by a fatty membrane and appearing as white granules, unlike the concentrated unprotected form, dissociates primarily in the lower parts of the intestine, which helps maintain the pH in the duodenum and jejunum at a low level favorable for the beneficial microflora characteristic of the small intestine [5].

Research results demonstrate the positive impact of mannanoligosaccharide-based products derived from yeast cells on the stability of intestinal microflora and poultry productivity [6]. In-depth practical knowledge gained in recent years in the feed industry through studies of the mechanism of action of mannan-based products (in particular, Bio-Mosa) has enabled the development of a product designed to achieve maximum effectiveness – Actigen, a unique bioactive fraction obtained from the outer cell wall of the yeast strain *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* [7].

The complex acidifier Sal-Zap is a mixture of propionic, acetic, and sorbic acids. In the feed industry, one of the main sources of Salmonella is animal proteins, particularly fishmeal. Sal-Zap has proven itself to be an effective inhibitor of pathogenic microflora growth during fishmeal production [8].

The literature we reviewed demonstrates positive performance improvements in poultry when using feed acidifiers and immunostimulants. However, data highlighting the in-depth study of organic acids and mannan-saccharides in terms of their impact on egg weight and morphology is almost absent. This underscores the novelty and relevance of our study.

The purpose of the study was to evaluate the effect of benzoic acid, mannanoligosaccharides, and Sal-Zap in compound feed for laying hens and quail on egg weight and morphological parameters.

To achieve this goal, the following objectives were set:

- to study the effect of benzoic acid in different forms, concentrated and coated, on the morphology of chicken eggs;
- to determine the effect of different doses of Sal-Zap on the morphological parameters of quail eggs.

Materials and Methods. The study on laying hens was conducted in the experimental poultry house of the Bashkir State Agrarian University, Ufa, Republic of Bashkortostan, Russia, from January to September 2025. The experiment lasted 9 months.

The quail experiments, lasting 7 months, were conducted from March to September 2025 at a quail farm in the Davlekanovsky District of the Republic of Bashkortostan.

For the first experiment, four groups of SuperNik laying hens, each containing 21 birds, were randomly selected. The birds were 245 days old at the beginning of the experiment. The second experiment was conducted on Manchurian quail. Fifty 46-day-old quail were selected. During the experiments, the birds were kept in standard windowless poultry houses, and the technological parameters of rearing, feeding, and maintenance complied with generally accepted standards.

The experiments were divided into two phases: preparatory and reporting. The preparatory phase (7 days before feeding the experimental feed) involved feeding all groups a base diet containing no micronutrients. During the reporting phase, the control groups also consumed the base feed, while the experimental groups were fed the following diets:

Experiment 1 (layers):

- Trial 1: 750 g concentrated benzoic acid per ton of feed + 200 g/t coated benzoic acid;

- Trial 2: 750 g concentrated benzoic acid + 200 g/t coated benzoic acid + 400 g/t mannanoligosaccharides as Actigen;

Experiment 2 (quail):

- Trial 1: Sal-Zap 500 g/t feed;
- Trial 2: 750 g/t;
- Trial 3: 1000 g/t.

Egg weight was determined gravimetrically every month, and egg morphology was determined in the final week of the experiment. The resulting digital data was processed using variation statistics in Microsoft Office Excel. The significance and magnitude of differences were assessed using Student's t-tests. Our research revealed a positive effect of using a combination of two forms of benzoic acid and the addition of mannanoligosaccharides on egg weight in laying hens (Figure 1). In the Trial 1, which tested a mixture of protected and concentrated benzoic acid, a significantly positive difference was observed compared to the control (+2.8%, $p < 0.001$). In the Trial 2, in addition to benzoic acid, we tested Actigen at the dosage that had shown the best results in the previous experiment. This combination resulted in an even greater increase in egg weight (+4.1% compared to the control, $p < 0.001$).

Figure 1. Egg Weight of Laying Hens, g

A detailed morphological analysis of the chicken eggs is presented in the Table 1. Absolute shell weight in the experimental groups significantly exceeded that in the control group (by 4.50% and 6.99%, $p < 0.001$). The relative shell weight to total egg weight was also higher in the experimental groups. Increased shell

weight is an indirect indicator of the shell's potential for impacts on the egg collection production line. Generally, higher shell weight indicates greater shell thickness, which, in turn, may predict greater shell strength. We also studied these parameters, found a positive correlation, and the data have been published elsewhere.

Table 1.

Morphological composition of laying hens' eggs

Indicator	Group		
	Control	Trial 1	Trial 2
Eggshell weight, mm	6,03±0,04	6,3±0,04 ^c	6,45±0,05 ^c
% to control	-	104,50	106,99
The ratio of eggshell mass to egg mass, %	10,26±0,06	10,41±0,07	10,52±0,06 ^b
% to control	-	101,46	102,61
Yolk weight, g	17,83±0,12	18,61±0,13 ^c	18,92±0,15 ^c
% to control	-	104,37	106,14
The ratio of the mass of the yolk to the mass of the egg, %	30,23±0,13	30,66±0,13 ^a	30,81±0,14 ^b
% to control	-	101,42	101,95
Albumen weight, r	35,14±0,27	35,77±0,21	36,08±0,3 ^a
% to control	-	101,77	102,65
Ratio of protein mass to egg mass, %	59,54±0,16	58,94±0,15	58,66±0,15
% to control	-	98,99	98,53

a - $p < 0,05$, b - $p < 0,01$, c - $p < 0,001$

Egg yolk weight is important from a nutritional perspective, as the majority of an egg's nutrients are concentrated in the yolk. In Experimental Trials 1 and 2, we observed significantly higher yolk weight than in the control group: by 4.37% and 6.14%, respectively ($p < 0.001$).

Furthermore, morphological analysis of the eggs revealed that the increase in shell and yolk content was due to a decrease in protein content (by 1.01% in Experimental Trial 1 and by 1.47% in Experimental Trial

2). However, as noted above (Figure 1), the total egg weight in the experimental groups was significantly higher than in the control.

In the quail laying experiment, in which Sal-Zap was tested as a feed acidifier at various dosages, we examined the same parameters as in the first experiment on chickens. Figure 2 shows the dynamics of changes in egg weight depending on the level of acidifier introduced into the feed.

Figure 2. Weight of quail eggs, g

The experimental groups with the tested dosages of 500 g/t, 750 g/t, and 1000 g/t outperformed the control group by 0.16 g (+1.43%), 0.42 g (+3.15%), and 0.17 g (+1.50%), respectively. We observed no additional benefits from using the highest of the tested dosages (1000 g/t), and the optimal dosage was determined to be 750 g of Sal-Zap per ton of compound feed.

Table 2 shows the changes in the morphological composition of quail eggs identified during the experiment. In quail egg farming, the issue of shell quality is even more pressing than in industrial chicken egg production, as the low shell strength of quail eggs is a naturally occurring factor. Although not a direct, eggshell weight is a reliable indicator of eggshell strength, so we carefully studied this parameter. Eggshell weight in the experimental groups was 0.75-2.99% higher than in the

control group, indicating improved nutrient metabolism in the groups consuming the Sal-Zap organic acid complex.

Table 2.

Indicator	Group			
	Control	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3
Eggshell weight, mm	1,34±0,02	1,35±0,01	1,38±0,02	1,36±0,01
% to control	-	100,75	102,99	101,49
The ratio of eggshell mass to egg mass, %	10,05±0,04	10,06±0,08	10,09±0,06	10,07±0,06
% to control	-	100,1	100,4	100,2
Yolk weight, g	4,10±0,05	4,17±0,05	4,28±0,06*	4,19±0,05
% to control	-	101,71	104,39	102,2
The ratio of the mass of the yolk to the mass of the egg, %	30,75±0,12	30,91±0,19	31,13±0,16	30,97±0,12
% to control	-	100,52	101,24	100,72
Albumen weight, r	7,89±0,09	7,99±0,11	8,09±0,12	7,98±0,09
% to control	-	101,27	102,53	101,14
Ratio of protein mass to egg mass, %	59,20±0,13	59,03±0,23	58,78±0,19	58,96±0,13
% to control	-	99,71	99,29	99,59

a - p<0,05

Improved absorption of feed nutrients, including vitamins, trace elements, and amino acids, was also reflected in yolk weight. The highest yolk weight among the tested doses was observed with the 750 g/t dose: 4.28 g versus 4.10 g in the control (+4.39%, p < 0.05).

Protein weight in the experimental samples was 0.29-0.71% lower than in the control, consistent with the results of the experiment on laying hens.

These data indicate that feeding egg-laying quail with the complex acidifier Sal-Zap provides significant benefits in terms of improved egg morphology. Sal-Zap, administered at 750 g/t, demonstrated the best results among the tested doses. Experiments have shown that feed acidification has a positive effect on egg weight, shell weight, and protein content in chicken and quail eggs produced for human consumption. These results indicate improved nutrient absorption due to modification of the bird's intestinal microflora by lowering the pH of the gastrointestinal tract. These observations are of practical importance for egg producers.

Conclusion. Studies of various feed acidifiers at varying dosages revealed positive trends in improving egg weight, shell weight, and yolk weight. The use of a combination of biologically active additives in laying hens' feed, including concentrated benzoic acid at 750 g/t of feed, coated benzoic acid at 200 g/t, and mannanoligosaccharides at 400 g/t, yields the best results. In quail feed, the complex preparation Sal-Zap is most appropriately used in the amount of 750 g/t of feed.

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